

Manuscript Number: CORSCI-D-13-01506R2

Title: Oxidation behavior of ZrB₂ composites doped with various transition metal silicides

Article Type: Full Length Article

Keywords: A. ZrB₂; A. silicides; B. SEM-EDX; C. high temperature corrosion; C. degradation.

Corresponding Author: Dr. Laura Silvestroni,

Corresponding Author's Institution: CNR

First Author: Laura Silvestroni

Order of Authors: Laura Silvestroni; Giacomo Meriggi; Diletta Sciti

Abstract: This paper deals with the oxidation behaviour of ZrB₂-based composites sintered with different additives, namely ZrSi₂, MoSi₂, TaSi₂ and WSi₂. The oxidation mechanisms were investigated between 1200 and 1800°C for 15 minutes in a bottom loading furnace. The scope of this study is to draw a classification of goodness for the 4 composites depending on the temperature range and understand how each cation influences the oxidation behaviour of ZrB₂ by acting either on glass or on ZrO₂ modification. MoSi₂ was the best additive for improving the oxidation resistance of ZrB₂, even up to 1800°C.

HIGHLIGHTS

Oxidation behavior of ZrB_2 composites doped with various transition metal silicides

Laura Silvestroni, Giacomo Meriggi, Diletta Sciti

- Oxidation of ZrB_2 - $MeSi_2$ ($Me = Zr, Mo, Ta, W$) at 1200-1800°C
- WSi_2 and $ZrSi_2$ have similar influence on the oxidation behavior of ZrB_2 up to 1650°C.
- $TaSi_2$ could be adequately used up to 1500°C, but above it is not suitable for ZrB_2 .
- $MoSi_2$ was the best additive of ZrB_2 , due the formation of a stable subsurface layer.

gas escape from the subsurface (Ta_2O_5 , B_2O_3 , SiO)

Oxidation behavior of ZrB₂ composites doped with various transition metal silicides

Laura Silvestroni^{*}, Giacomo Meriggi, Diletta Sciti

CNR-ISTEC, Institute of Science and Technology for Ceramics, Via Granarolo 64, I-48018 Faenza, Italy

Abstract

This paper deals with the oxidation behaviour of ZrB₂-based composites sintered with different additives, namely ZrSi₂, MoSi₂, TaSi₂ and WSi₂. The oxidation mechanisms were investigated between 1200 and 1800°C for 15 minutes in a bottom loading furnace. The scope of this study is to draw a classification of goodness for the 4 composites depending on the temperature range and understand how each cation influences the oxidation behaviour of ZrB₂ by acting either on glass or on ZrO₂ modification. MoSi₂ was the best additive for improving the oxidation resistance of ZrB₂, even up to 1800°C.

Key words: ultra-high temperature ceramics, ZrB₂, silicides, oxidation resistance, degradation phenomena.

1. Introduction

Zirconium diboride, ZrB₂, is one of the most investigated material in the ultra-high temperature ceramic (UHTC) class in view of its interesting combination of physico-chemical and engineeristic properties [1,2]. The good mechanical strength of ZrB₂-composites has been assessed in various works [3,4] and superior resistance at high temperature has been also reported upon addition of suitable additives [5,6,7]. However, clear reasons explaining this good behavior at high temperature have not been stated yet. Literature review shows that the introduction of cations of transition metal in form of silicide or carbide, strongly modifies the high temperature performances and the oxidation behavior of ZrB₂, but data are not directly comparable owing to different compositions, oxidation conditions and specimen size.

The oxidation behavior of monolithic ZrB₂ has been object of numerous investigations [8] and all the studies assessed that the main reactions involve the formation of glassy B₂O₃, at low temperature, and porous crystalline ZrO₂, according to (1):

Boron oxide, tends to evaporate around 1300°C, depending on the oxygen partial pressure, leaving an open skeleton of ZrO₂. This develops in shape of tiny rounded particles on the boride grains and undergoes notable grain coarsening above 1500°C. It has been stated that the oxidation behavior is dominated by parabolic kinetics despite formation of a porous oxide of the refractory metal [8]. This protective behavior is attributed to the borosilicate glass that fills the pores of the porous oxide scale and often also results in a glassy external layer. The main issues in the oxidation of ZrB₂ at temperature below 2000°C consist in the

* Corresponding author: L. Silvestroni
Tel. +39 546 699723
Fax. +39 546 46381
e-mail. laura.silvestroni@istec.cnr.it

formation of a porous ZrO_2 scale, which allows continuous penetration of oxygen through the bulk, and in the large volume expansion associated to the polytypic transformation of ZrO_2 [9]. The addition of SiC [10-13] or silicides of transition metals [14-16] notably modifies the oxidation behavior of monolithic ZrB_2 , through the formation of a silico-boride glass, whose viscosity can be modified by the incorporation or dissolution of the relevant cation [14-16], or even through the change of the physical properties of ZrO_2 , which can melt at lower temperature and form a compact dense external scale [17].

In the present work, several transition metal disilicides, $MeSi_2$, were added to a ZrB_2 matrix in order to study how each cation modifies the oxidation performances of this UHTC. The additives object of this study include $ZrSi_2$, $MoSi_2$, $TaSi_2$ and WSi_2 .

1.1 Effect of $MeSi_2$ on the oxidation of ZrB_2 composites

In this paragraph, the effect of transition metal silicides on the oxidation behavior of ZrB_2 and ZrB_2 -SiC composites is briefly reviewed.

In a study by Lavrenko et al. [18] it was assessed that at $1200^\circ C$ the addition of $ZrSi_2$ improved the oxidation behavior of monolithic ZrB_2 and further surpassed the $MoSi_2$ and WSi_2 high-temperature materials in oxidation resistance. The effect of $MoSi_2$ on the oxidation resistance of ZrB_2 has been studied through thermogravimetric analyses up to $1400^\circ C$ for 30 hours revealing parabolic kinetics at $1400^\circ C$, due to the formation of a compact silica-based scale and subsurface oxidation with formation of refractory species, like MoB [19]. Similar oxidation products were observed upon oxidation at $1400^\circ C$ for 100 hours in conventional kilns [20]. A successive work reported different oxidation stages for HfB_2 doped with $TaSi_2$, revealing formation of a layered oxide scale based on $Hf_6Ta_2O_{17}$ crystals embedded in a silica layer upon oxidation at $1600^\circ C$ for 15 min in conventional air furnace [21]. In a very recent paper [22], the oxidation behavior of ZrB_2 with 0, 4, 6, or 8 mol% W was investigated at 800 – $1600^\circ C$ and pointed out that the addition of W into B_2O_3 increased the stability of the protective glassy layer, which resulted in higher oxidation resistance.

Most of the works in the literature, consider the effect of silicides addition in ZrB_2 -SiC composites, however, being SiC a major phase, in amount 10-40 vol%, it is difficult to discriminate the action of the silicide alone.

For example, the effect of $ZrSi_2$ on the oxidation resistance of ZrB_2 -SiC ceramics has been studied up to $1700^\circ C$ in air by thermogravimetric analysis coupled with differential thermal analysis and it has been concluded that addition of small amounts of this silicide, 7 vol%, substantially slow down the oxidation of the ceramic due to the stabilization of the upper oxide layer of borosilicate glass [23]. A model for ZrB_2 -SiC- $ZrSi_2$ ceramics during long-term oxidation at $1500^\circ C$ has been also developed and validated by experiments, confirming a parabolic behavior. The reason ascribed to the improved performances was related to decreased oxygen diffusion rate in the subsurface layer [24].

ZrB₂-SiC-MoSi₂ ceramics were studied at 1500°C for 10 hours and the results confirmed good oxidation behavior, as previously pointed out for ZrB₂-SiC and ZrB₂-MoSi₂ composites [25].

Concerning the effect of tantalum, other authors [26-29] pointed out that Ta-addition is beneficial up to 1600°C by acting both on zirconium oxide and glass properties. As for the first effect, Ta, with a higher valence cation than Zr, can stuff oxygen vacancy in Zr oxide. The presence of fewer vacancies in the refractory oxide makes it more stable and thus the tetragonal/monoclinic phase transformation is circumvented together with the volume expansion associated and thus possibility to form cracks in the scale is reduced too. As far as the glass is concerned, the borosilicate glass becomes more viscous due to the higher cation strength field of tantalum inducing immiscibility and the formation of a more viscous external layer possessing higher boiling point and preventing oxygen inward diffusion. However Tantalum is reported to become detrimental above 1600°C [28] due to the melting of Ta₂O₅ and to the formation of a complex orthorhombic Zr-Ta-oxide which has a needle-like morphology not favorable for adhesion to the unoxidized bulk.

As for WSi₂ additions, there are no reports on its effect on the oxidation. However, beneficial effects of W-compounds on the oxidation behavior of ZrB₂ and ZrB₂-SiC composites have been already outlined in [6,22,30]. W-doping was introduced in ZrB₂-SiC composites in form of carbide in amounts ranging from 3 to 7 vol% and increased performances of the W-doped ceramics as compared to pure ZrB₂-SiC was reported in all cases. The reasons ascribed to this improvement rely on the formation of an eutectic between WO₃ and ZrO₂ at 1275°C, that acted as liquid phase sintering and decreased the porosity of the scale [6,30], or WO₃ itself acted as barrier due to the volume increase associated with oxidation of W to WO₃ [30], and finally W increased the stability of the borate glass retarding its evaporation [22]. Other authors suggested that tungsten oxide species form strong acid sites on ZrO₂ and inhibit ZrO₂ crystallite tetragonal to monoclinic structural transformations. [31].

The scope of this work is hence a direct comparison of various silicides effect on the oxidation of ZrB₂. The rationale behind this work is that a better understanding of the basic oxidation mechanisms of ZrB₂ doped with MeSi₂ will lead to the development of better and more refractory composites, or to the definition of safety temperature ranges for each composite.

2. Experimental procedure

ZrB₂-based composites were prepared using the following commercial powders: hexagonal ZrB₂, Grade B (H.C. Starck, Germany), specific surface area 1.0 m²/g, impurity max content: C: 0.25 wt%, O: 2 wt%, N: 0.25 wt%, Fe: 0.1 wt%, Hf: 0.2 wt%, particle size range 0.1-8 μm; orthorhombic ZrSi₂-F (Japan New Metals Co., LTD, Osaka, Japan) particle size 2-5 μm, C>0.15, Fe>0.30, O>1.00; tetragonal MoSi₂ (<2 μm, Aldrich, Steinbeim, Germany), particle size range 0.3-5 μm and oxygen content ~1 wt %; hexagonal TaSi₂

(ABCR, GmbH & Co, Karlsruhe, Germany), particle size <45 μm ; tetragonal WSi_2 (Sigma Aldrich, Milano), - 325 mesh, 99.5%, traces of metals <6000 ppm.

Compositions containing 15 vol% of silicide were prepared by conventional wet milling route and sintered by hot pressing to full density, as reported in [5]. For the sake of clarity, Tab. I summarizes the sintering conditions and the main microstructural features of the 4 composites.

Oxidation tests were carried out in a bottom-up loading furnace (Nannetti FC18, Faenza, Italy and Carbolite BLF1800 furnace, Hope Valley, UK) at 1200, 1350, 1500 and 1650°C for 15 minutes on rectangular 13 mm x 2.5 mm x 2 mm bars in static air. For the best compositions, further tests at 1800°C were performed. Specimens were located in the furnace when the maximum temperature was achieved and then removed and air-quenched after the exposure time. The mass and dimensions of the bars were measured before and after the oxidation. The as-sintered material and oxidized specimens were examined on the surface using X-ray diffraction (Bruker D8 Advance, Bruker, Karlsruhe, Germany) to identify the crystalline phases.

The microstructures before and after oxidation were analyzed using field emission gun scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, Carl Zeiss Sigma NTS GmbH Oberkochen, Germany) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS, INCA Energy 300, Oxford Instruments, UK) on surface and fractured cross-section of the specimens to reveal modifications induced by oxidation.

3 Results

3.1. As sintered microstructure

In order to understand the microstructural evolution upon oxidation at the various temperatures, it is useful to briefly summarize the compositional structure of the as sintered composites. For some materials, a thorough characterization can be found in [5,32], but the main features are reported in Tab. I.

ZBZ - This material was fully densified at 1600°C. A polished surface of ZBZ is reported in Fig. 1a, evidencing mean grain size of 2.5 μm and the secondary phases: 3.2 ZrO_2 , 3.0 ZrSi_2 , 1.5 SiO_2 -based species and 1.3 SiC . No wetted grain boundaries were noticed by SEM and TEM inspections. Often, SiO_2 pockets surrounding elongated SiC crystals were found.

ZBM - This ceramic achieved the full density at 1750°C, Table I. In Fig. 1b, ZrB_2 had mean grain size around 2.5 μm and the matrix had a peculiar morphology with ZrB_2 grains displaying a core-shell substructure. The core was constituted by original ZrB_2 grains and the shell by a $(\text{Zr},\text{Mo})\text{B}_2$ solid solution, with an amount of Mo around 5 at%, which grew epitaxially on the core [32]. The phase with white contrast, often located at the tips of MoSi_2 , is MoB or Mo-Si-B phase, in amount below 2%. Silica pockets, around 4 vol%, were recognizable as dark contrasting phases. Small amounts, below 2% of ZrO_2 , ZrC, and spurious Zr-C-O phase were also detected.

ZBT - This composite required 1850°C to achieve the full density. An example of polished surface of ZBT is shown in Fig. 1c. ZrB₂ grains had an average size of about 2 μm and, similarly to ZBM, these grains were surrounded by a (Zr,Ta)B₂ solid solution, which appeared lighter in color (inset in Fig. 1c). According to quantitative EDS analysis and XRD, the composition of this solid solution was (Zr_{0.8}Ta_{0.2})B₂ [5]. Pure TaSi₂ was not clearly identified in the composite, but bright Ta_xSi_y phases were observed in amount around 5 vol%. About 1.6 vol% of ZrO₂ particles were also found along with 2 vol% of silica-based phases containing various impurities. Spurious carbide phases, such as Zr-Ta-C, SiC, or Si-C-O, were also detected in limited amounts, below 2 vol%.

ZBW – 1900°C were necessary to densify this composite, owing to a more refractory silicide. The microstructure of the material sintered with WSi₂ is depicted in Fig. 1d. Also this composite displayed a core-shell morphology: pure ZrB₂ constitutes the core and a (Zr,W)B₂ solid solution the shell, with a W content around 2 at% and mean grain size in the order of 3.5 μm. Large agglomerates of white phases, in amount around 3.5 vol%, were identified as WC and W-C-O with (Zr,W)_xSi_y and (Zr,W)B as terminal parts in triangular shape. About 2.8 vol% of SiO₂ pockets trapping ZrO₂ particles were observed too.

3.2. Microstructure upon oxidation

3.2.1 Appearance and weight gain

A picture of the specimen after oxidation tests between 1200 and 1800°C is shown in Fig. 2, where it can be seen that increasing the oxidation temperature, the grey color, typical of the as sintered bars first on the left, moves to dark grey, index of glass formation, to whitish-yellow, indicating the presence of mostly ZrO₂. It is worthy to note that ZBM was the least damaged material, preserving the darkest color even at 1800°C. On the contrary, the most damaged sample was ZBT, which finished the 1650°C test with compromised shape and evident bubbling on the surface.

The weight gain per unit surface area as a function of the oxidation temperature, plotted in Fig. 3, increased with the temperature for all composites and confirmed the results suggested by visual inspection, even after oxidation at 1800°C, ZBM was the least damaged and ZBT the most damaged at 1650°C. Up to 1500°C the material gaining the highest weight was ZBZ, followed by ZBW, ZBT and ZBM. Above this temperature the trend changed: ZBT abruptly increased, ZBZ and ZBW were almost comparable, whereas ZBM arrived to the highest temperature with a weight gain around one third as compared to the other composites.

3.2.2 X-ray diffraction

Tab. II reports the crystalline phases detected by XRD on the various specimens at the different oxidation temperature.

The main crystalline oxidation product in ZBZ was monoclinic zirconia at all temperatures, the tetragonal polytype was present too but in minor amount and ZrB_2 peaks remained evident up to 1350°C.

Also for ZBM composite, the main crystalline phase was monoclinic ZrO_2 , but ZrB_2 reflections remained visible even after oxidation at all temperatures, although just in traces after 1650°C. $MoSi_2$ peaks disappeared after oxidation at 1350°C leaving instead tetragonal MoB phase. The high temperature ZrO_2 polytype appeared after oxidation at 1350°C and increased in intensity with the oxidation temperature. No clear Mo_5Si_3 phase was identified. At 1800°C, besides monoclinic and tetragonal ZrO_2 , MoO_3 was also clearly identified.

The x-ray diffraction patterns for ZBT were quite diverse depending on the oxidation temperature, as Fig.4 shows. At 1200°C, monoclinic ZrO_2 was the major phase, but peaks relative to the boride were well visible and those corresponding to the $(Zr,Ta)B_2$ solid solution seemed more intense as compared to the pure ZrB_2 , in addition TaB_2 peaks and mixed Zr-Ta oxide with orthorhombic structure and formula $TaZr_{2.75}O_8$ were found too. At 1350°C, the main phase was still m- ZrO_2 , but TaB_2 peaks clearly emerged whilst ZrB_2 reflections decreased in intensity. When the composite was oxidized at 1500°C, the mixed oxide was the main phase, which showed evident crystal orientation along the [200] planes, monoclinic ZrO_2 and TaB_2 followed. Increasing the oxidation temperature to 1650°C the preferential orientation of $TaZr_{2.75}O_8$ changed along the [020] planes and, besides ZrO_2 , orthorhombic Ta_2O_5 formed.

Moving to ZBW composite, monoclinic ZrO_2 and hexagonal ZrB_2 were present up to 1350°C, from this temperature on, only Zr-oxides were found. Traces of tetragonal ZrO_2 were detected at all temperatures. No clear evidence of tungsten oxide was detected. At 1800°C, monoclinic ZrO_2 was the major crystalline phase and the tetragonal phase was present just in traces.

3.2.3 SEM - EDS analyses

In the following, the microstructural details observed on the external surface and on the fractured cross section will be presented for each composite, Fig.5-8. Scale thickness as calculated from SEM analyses is reported in Fig. 9.

ZBZ – The external surface of ZrB_2 doped with $ZrSi_2$ after oxidation at 1200°C was completely covered by a continuous borosilicate glass from which 500 nm ZrO_2 grains emerged from time to time, as Fig. 5a shows. An increase of the oxidation temperature to 1350°C resulted in a thickening of the external silica glass, where boron was not detected anymore and the ZrO_2 grains were less abundant, Fig. 5b. The same phases were observed after test at 1500°C, but the amount of protruding ZrO_2 increased and assumed the shape of platelets, petals or tiny rods, Fig. 5c. At 1650°C the surface was very similar to that observed at 1500°C, but in the edges region the petal-like ZrO_2 was more frequent than the horns, which was instead more abundant in the center of the specimen, Fig. 5d.

Images of the cross section of ZBZ are reported below in Fig. 5. Overall, the oxidized sections reveal compact scales with no porosity. Already at 1200°C, Fig. 5a, about 1 µm thick of continuous silica layer covered a 18 µm sublayer of rounded fine zirconia. In the following 10 µm inward, bulk material with intergranular zirconia around ZrB₂ grains was found. At 1350°C, Fig. 5b, the external silica layer thickened just to 2 µm, then a 15 µm of coarse ZrO₂ filled with silica was standing above 30 µm of ZrB₂ with intergranular fine ZrO₂. Increasing the oxidation temperature to 1500°C, Fig. 5c, the outermost 10 µm were composed by SiO₂ glassy phase topping ZrO₂ crystals. Right beneath this scale, 100 µm of dense ZrO₂ phase with SiO₂ pokets was found. The last oxidation temperature, 1600°C, Fig. 5d, resulted in the formation of a 7 µm dense silica scale from which ZrO₂ rods emerged on the top (inset in Fig. 5d). Then about 50 µm were constituted by elongated ZrO₂ grains filled with SiO₂. Moving further inward, the microstructure was mainly columnar ZrO₂ for about 120 µm, which became rounded for 30 µm and this phase stood on a mixed ZrB₂ scale, around 35 µm thick, containing intergranular ZrO₂ and notable amount of SiO₂.

ZBM – The external surface of ZrB₂ doped with MoSi₂ after oxidation is shown in upper part of Fig. 6. After oxidation at 1200°C, a continuous silica layer formed on the top and tiny crystal of ZrO₂ could be occasionally found immersed in, Fig.6a. Traces of molybdenum oxide and evidence of Ca-rich immiscible glass could be found as well. Oxidation at 1350°C induced the formation of higher amount of ZrO₂ precipitates on the continuous silica scale, Fig.6b. The same microstructural features were observed after oxidation at 1500°C, where preferential glass removal at the edges was observed, Fig.6c. The same holds true for oxidation at 1650°C, Fig.6d, where ZrO₂ nanoprecipitates and aggregates were floating on continuous silica scale. **The surface of the specimen oxidized at 1800°C still showed a continuous glassy scale with some very large transparent bubbles, Fig. 2b. SEM inspection revealed the silica glass in the dark areas and zirconia where the bubble exploded. At the glass-zirconia interface, MoO₃ grains in platelet shape were observed, as illustrated in Fig. 6e.**

Images of the cross section of ZBM are reported in the bottom part of Fig.6. After oxidation at 1200°C, Fig.6a, a continuous silica layer was covering about 2.5 µm of fine graded ZrO₂ and right underneath, MoSi₂ oxidation products, like SiO₂ pockets coated by tiny MoB/Mo₅Si₃ particles, were found in ZrB₂. A temperature increase of 150°C left an almost unaffected thickness of silica and zirconia, but induced the migration of further silica close to the upper surface in a spin shape, Fig.6b, indicating that at this temperature silica is very fluid. The cross section of ZBM at 1500°C in Fig.6c shows a thickening of ZrO₂ layer, whilst the continuous external coating remained almost around a couple of micron thick. Underneath the silica spin, SiO₂ and MoB could be easily found in a striped shape always adjacent one another immersed in ZrB₂ and the total altered thickness passed from 4 µm at 1200°C to 25 µm at 1500°C. At 1650°C, Fig.6d, the outermost silica layer was crossed through by zirconia grains and its thickness increased to about 25 µm, the ZrB₂-SiO₂-MoB layer resulted around 40 µm and then the bulk ceramic started. **The cross section of ZBM oxidized at 1800°C is shown in Fig. 6f. The outermost scale is composed by 50 µm of**

compact ZrO_2 and silica with some cavities due to bubbling. Underneath this layer, bright MoB chain separates other 65 μm of columnar ZrO_2 crossed by silico-boride glass. Then ZrB_2 starts with SiO_2 and MoB phases, similarly to the previous samples before finding the unreacted bulk.

ZBT – The external surface of this ceramic after oxidation in the 1200-1650°C temperature range is shown in Fig.7, upper part. At 1200°C, the specimen was covered by a continuous SiO_2 -based layer with B_2O_3 traces and tiny aggregates of ZrO_2 particles. No Ta was detected both in the glass and in the crystalline particles. At 1350°C the ZrO_2 aggregates increased in dimensions from 500 nm to 6 μm and boron was not detected anymore in the glass. The surface after exposure at 1500°C appeared completely changed: most of the surface was occupied by a crystalline mixed oxide, $ZrTa_{2.7}O_8$, with petal-like shape, and this structure was filled by silica. The crystals were in turn covered with brighter dendritic structures richer in tantalum. At 1650°C the sample underwent a second drastic change: the mixed Zr-Ta-oxide was lifted by the outgassing volatile species and the platelets assumed a vertical position immersed in the silica-based glass. Large craters were present too. This mixed oxide was disposed in geometrical shape and was covered by small dendritic Ta_2O_5 crystals, Fig.7d.

The cross sections of the oxidized ZBT samples are reported in Fig.7, bottom part. The sample oxidized at 1200°C involved less than 10 μm thick with an outermost continuous silica scale, a thin layer of fine grained ZrO_2 and other about 5 μm of boride matrix containing the oxidation products of the sintering additive, like SiO_2 and Ta_2O_5 , Fig.7a. At 1350°C the silica layer slightly thickened and tended to detach from the underlying zirconia, which involved around 20 μm of material, Fig.7b. In this scale, SiO_2 and Ta_2O_5 were still present and recognizable as dark and white phases, respectively. TaB_2 was present too as white phase. At 1500°C, Fig.7c, the silica scale thickness doubled and completely surrounded the Zr-Ta-oxide crystals; differently from the previous sample, no spalling was observed between glass and zirconia. Underneath this layer, about 25 μm of ZrO_2 with bright tantalum oxide and boride white agglomerates were found next to silica pockets. The oxidation at 1650°C provoked catastrophic microstructural evolution in ZBT, Fig.7d. About 500 μm from the external surface were composed by ZrO_2 and Ta_2O_5 partially filled with silica glass where bubbles and craters involved the whole thickness. The ZrO_2 grains were coated with dendritic Ta_2O_5 , as shown in the upper inset of Fig.7d, and in the region right underneath these crystals grew in a spike-pillar shape, like reported in the second inset of Fig. 7d. This thick scale was standing above a 10 μm layer of dense zirconia interposed by bright TaB_2 particles standing adjacent to SiO_2 . Then other 10 μm of material were composed by ZrO_2 with intergranular Ta_2O_5 .

ZBW – The external surfaces of the sample containing WSi_2 oxidized at all temperatures are reported in Fig.8, upper part. The surface of the specimen oxidized at 1200°C appeared covered by B_2O_3 and silica glass where sub-micrometric zirconia grains were dispersed in. These were covered by a W-O-based dendritic network and interposed with 500 nm aggregates of bright WO_3 grains, Fig.8a. **The fact that**

W-oxides were not found by XRD on this sample, is probably due to its amount below the detection limit of the instrument (5 vol%), or because of its morphology as discontinuous whiskers on ZrO₂ grains, Fig. 8a.

At 1350°C boron oxide disappeared and the surface remained composed by ZrO₂ grains immersed in silica glass. Also the W-signal was barely detected among the crystals. The oxidation at 1500°C induced a notable variation of the external morphology which appeared wavy and quite irregular showing craters and cabbage-like structures, Fig.8b. The ZrO₂ grains coarsened to about 2 μm, the growing planes were well visible and appeared aggregated and melted on a silica continuous layer. At the grain boundary, W-rich phases with bright contrast were present, Fig.8c. The aspect of the sample oxidized at 1650°C was not notably different from the one oxidized at 1500°C, just more bumps and craters were noticed, Fig.8d. An increase of the oxidation temperature up to 1800°C provoked notable damage to the ZBW sample, it was completely covered by white oxide and SEM analyses evidenced cracking and vigorous bubbling in the ZrO₂-SiO₂ outermost scale, Fig. 8e.

The cross sections of the oxidized ZBW samples are shown in Fig.8, bottom part. After oxidation at 1200°C a discontinuous silica scale was standing on top of a fine-grained zirconia scale where bright rounded W-O-based particles were dispersed in, Fig.8a. This scale, less than 25 μm thick, was well adherent to the unreacted bulk. An increase of the oxidation to 1350°C doubled the thickness of the oxidized scale as compared to the previous sample, which maintained however the same morphology, Fig.8b. Also in this case the oxidized layer was well anchored to the matrix, thanks to the growth of the oxide well integrated onto the boride grains, inset in Fig.8b. The oxidation at 1500°C, Fig.8c, induced a diversification in morphologies of the ZrO₂ sub layer. Starting from the top, 20 μm coarse ZrO₂ grains were standing on other 20 μm columnar ZrO₂, which was topping about 95 μm of dense rounded-grains ZrO₂. The whole thickness was partially filled with silica and the oxide grains were coated with homogeneously dispersed WO₃ drops which eventually turned into agglomerates where enough porosity among ZrO₂ grains let enough room for their condensation as 5 μm particles, see the insets in Fig.8c. At 1650°C the morphology of the various scale remained basically unmodified as compared to the features observed for the samples oxidized at 1500°C, Fig. 8d, but each scale just increased in thickness. Another feature worthy of mentioning is the formation of small cracks within columnar ZrO₂ grains. At 1800°C the sample resulted much damaged, about 400 μm of material underwent oxidation, Fig.8f. The outermost scale was composed by large ZrO₂ grains fissured and partially filled with silica-based glass. This thick layer was standing on top of a denser scale made of ZrO₂ with elongated shape filled by white WO₃ particles and veined by B₂O₃ glass, Fig.8g. The presence of borates at such high temperature could be due to the stabilization of the glass by W, as reported in [22]. This scale was completely spalled from the bulk.

4 Discussion

An impression at glance of the beneficial or detrimental effect of each silicide is provided in Fig.9 which reports the modified thickness of the four composites after oxidation, where for oxidized thickness we intend the depth of material containing oxidation products, either of the diboride, or the silicide. The plot is in good agreement with the weight gain in Fig.3, i.e. larger weight gain is associated to a thicker oxide layer, suggesting that any of the two indicators, weight gain or thickness, could be used as representative of oxidation degree.

Multiple and various phenomena occur upon oxidation of ZrB_2 doped with various $MeSi_2$ implying melting, formation of glassy phases, phase transformation and volatilization. Such mechanisms depend on the chemico-physical nature and content of the silicide after sintering. The oxidation products of the silicides are also function of the valence of the cation, which will form solid, volatile or instable oxides and will interact with the boride matrix and its oxidation products. Fig. 3,9 and microstructural characterization evidence similarities, but also strong differences amongst the systems analyzed. All the systems develop a complex multilayered scale basically containing ZrO_2 -based oxides, whilst the silicides provide some partially protective silica-based oxide scales. Strong oxidation phenomena involve the three systems from 1650°C on, whilst ZBM remains more unaffected from oxidation, with effects similar to what already reported in the literature [20,26]. In the subsurface layer, no depletion layer is ever observed for any of these systems. Remarkably, addition of $MoSi_2$ and $TaSi_2$ retard the formation of columnar ZrO_2 , which is typical of ZrB_2 or ZrB_2 -SiC oxidation [8,10-13]. Columnar ZrO_2 is observed for ZBZ and ZBW starting from 1500°C, whilst for ZBM appears only upon oxidation at 1800°C.

In the following, discussion will compare the materials response at each temperature, keeping in mind three fundamental aspects affecting the oxidation processes:

- a. content, composition and chemical stability of the silicide phase after sintering, as silica-forming phase. Due to the silicide reactivity during sintering the chemico-physical nature and content of silicide after densification can be significantly different compared to the starting composition, as illustrated in paragraph 3.1. Low melting silicides are for instance present in ZBZ [33]. In ZBZ, ZBT and ZBW the final content of silicide is drastically reduced from 15 to 3-5 vol%, whilst in ZBM remains basically unchanged, 14 vol%, indicating that $MoSi_2$ is the most stable silicides with the lowest tendency to dissociate.
- b. the type of cation introduced with the silicide. Possible cations effects on glass modification have been already outlined in the paragraph 1.1. In this work, Mo Ta or W are potentially able to modify the glass composition and viscosity.
- c. events occurring in the subsurface layer. Although the surface morphology presents similarities, at least for three composites, the cross sections reveal different species formed, as the aforementioned columnar ZrO_2 .

A direct comparison of the four systems reveals the following features.

1200°C - At this temperature, all the four composites display similar behavior, with an outer borosilicate layer where ZrO₂ particles are dispersed in and this layer is generally continuous.

The four silicides are expected to oxidize according to:

In this temperature range, a subsurface oxidation layer is formed in all system, mainly composed of ZrO₂, for a thickness below 10 μm for ZBM and ZBT, and around 30 μm for ZBZ and ZBW. The different thickness could be related to the actual silicide amount, in the case of ZBM, and to the formation of a more viscous glass in the case of ZBT. ZBW seems the most damaged probably owing to the lower content of Si-species.

1350°C - The picture remains essentially the same, as the four materials still display a similar behavior even if ZBZ and ZBW exhibit a thicker oxide scale compared to the other systems. This is due to the starting of formation of a subsurface layer in ZBM and ZBT containing solid and stable products at these temperatures, like MoB and TaB₂, as discussed below.

1500°C - The four materials begin to remarkably differentiate their oxidation behavior. ZBZ and ZBW start to oxidize readily and both weight gain and oxide thickness reach similar values. ZBM and ZBT have lower oxidation rates, ZBM being the most resistant. This behavior is probably due to the refractoriness of secondary phases. The composite doped with ZrSi₂ contains an amount of non-stoichiometric zirconium silicides with low melting points, around or even lower than 1500°C. Thus in the material's bulk, liquid phases can arise from Zr_xSi_y melting.

For WSi₂ additions, liquid phase can be already present at temperatures lower than 1300°C, due to the aforementioned WO₃-ZrO₂ eutectic [34]. Additional sources of liquid come from mixed (Zr,W)-silicides, oxides and carbides present as secondary phases in the sintered microstructure [35]. Liquid phases, both in ZBZ and ZBW bulk, provide a fast path for oxygen transport and enhance oxidation. For ZBW composite, the condensation of tungsten oxide from vapor phase is well evident, as this phase is found as nanosized rounded particles on ZrO₂ grains, Fig.8c,d, therefore tungsten oxide is supposed to come from reactions (5) or (6). As a matter of fact, differently from ZBT, the formation of solid solutions in ZBW between W and zirconia was not proved by SEM-EDS nor X-ray diffraction, so reaction (6) is possible, too.

The addition of MoSi₂ has been previously discussed [19,20]. First of all, secondary phases such as MoB and Mo₅Si₃ are already present in small amounts after sintering, but, differently from residual Zr_xSi_y detected in

ZBZ, they and are highly refractory with melting point overpassing 2000°C [36]. Oxygen penetration in the subsurface layer favors further formation of these species, according to reactions (3) and (7), where B₂O₃ in (7) derives from ZrB₂ oxidation in (1).

The addition of TaSi₂ at this temperature showed beneficial effects on the oxidation behavior, limiting the weight gain and also the degradation of a thick scale. This is probably due to similar mechanisms taking place for MoSi₂. Indeed, TaB₂ and SiO₂ were found next to each other's. Thus, formation of TaB₂ can occur according to:

Presence of solid species instead of liquid phases retards the subsurface oxidation, explaining the lower scale thickness of both ZBM and ZBT. In particular, TaB₂ is reported to be an excellent oxidation resistance material up to this temperature [37].

TaSi₂ is a very peculiar additive, leading to a complex microstructure already upon sintering, thus signing its marked tendency to dissociate and enter in solid solution into ZrB₂ lattice. During oxidation it forms silica and an orthorhombic metal oxide according to reaction (4). For this composite, in addition to reaction (1) and (4), also the oxidation reaction of the solid solution has to be considered and can be expressed as (9), bringing to the formation of a mixed orthorhombic oxide:

The chemico-physical properties of this mixed phase are not completely known, however it has been reported to possess lower melting point as compared to that of ZrO₂ [28]. The exact mechanism leading to the formation of this platelet oxide on the surface is not completely understood yet and could also be due to the dissolution of the simple oxides into the silico-boride glass and to the following precipitation as complex oxide, as (10) shows:

1650°C - at this temperature, the aforementioned phenomena are further enhanced. Liquid phases in ZBZ and ZBW cause convection phenomena which make zirconia grow in the form of columns, as consequence of convective transport of low viscosity borosilicate liquid, similar to what observed for ZrB₂-SiC composites [10-13]. The outer silica layer, where Zr is almost no soluble in, tends to evaporate and pillar-like ZrO₂ features develops on the surface, Fig.5d,8d, owing to the vigorous gas escape. Although WSi₂ and ZrSi₂ are characterized by different melting points, which should affect the oxidation behavior in different ways, the practical effect of the two silicides up to 1650°C is very similar in terms of weight gain, scale thickness and oxide morphology. The minimum amount of W that is reported to be effective in promoting liquid phase sintering of ZrO₂ and thus hindering the oxidation, was reported to be 4 mol% [17]. In the current case, about 10 mol% are present in the composite so well above the minimum required for densification, but in

the investigated temperature range, the superiority of ZBW is not so marked. As a matter of fact, the oxidation protection imparted by W addition is reported to be better above 1600°C [17] or even above 1800°C [38].

To the highest step of the podium stands ZBM, which results in the composite with best oxidation resistance at all temperatures. For this material, it seems that the evolution of gaseous phases is prevented up to 1650°C. Possible reasons could be related to the reduction of B₂O₃ content in the subsurface liquid through reaction with MoSi₂ to form solid MoB, reaction (7). Compared to pure SiO₂, the addition of B₂O₃ decreases the liquid viscosity and its diffusion towards the surface is slower. In addition, the dissolution of little amount of Mo into the silica scale, which is actually reported to acts as a reticulating agent in glass structure [39], could further increase the viscosity of the liquid phases. This combination of mechanisms could explain why formation of columnar ZrO₂ is suppressed in this composite.

Finally, in ZBT, phenomena similar to those in ZBM could occur, but this is not the case. First of all, the formation of TaB₂ did not ensure any further oxidation stability, as this compound was reported to quickly vaporize at 1650°C [37]. Moreover, the oxidation behavior is dominated by the formation of the mixed Zr,Ta oxide whose formation is accompanied by a notable volume expansion. Another evident feature is the marked gas evolution above 1500°C which causes the rotation of the TaZr_{2.75}O₈ platelets in vertical position, thus keeping open channels to further oxygen inward. The volume expansion, as well as the lower amount of available silica, explains the absence of continuous silica coverage, different from what observed for lower temperature oxidation. Accelerated oxidation led to a marked increase of the weight gain and thickness of the oxidized layer making this as the least resistant composite.

The main mechanisms occurring in the four composites in the 1200-1650°C temperature range are sketched in Fig. 10.

1800°C – The oxidation in this more severe temperature regime evidenced that in ZBW no stable dense and compact external layer formed, but, on the contrary, continuous migration of silica species and W-oxides to the top surface induced the formation of craters and fissures, owing to a too dynamic gas escape.

As for the system containing MoSi₂, this temperature eventually induced the formation of columnar ZrO₂, owing to boiling of glasses. However the continuous silica scale on the top prevented an extreme weight loss, which remained in the same range or even below that of the other system oxidized at 1500°C, and, accordingly, limited the thickness of the modified layer, which did not overpassed that of the other systems oxidized at 1650°C. The continuous subtraction of B₂O₃ to preferentially form MoB, instead of diffusing into the silica glass and thus decreasing its viscosity, could be one of the main reasons of the good oxidation behavior of this compound. In addition, the high stability of MoB phase is confirmed by its presence in form of cordillera at the interface between columnar ZrO₂ and outer silica scale, first inset in Fig. 6f. It seems that

at 1800°C and at low partial pressure, MoB starts to oxidize according to reaction (11), as we observe its dissolution in silica in the second inset of Fig. 6f.

Then the glass becomes more liquid and induces the formation of ZrO₂ pillar. But as long as the oxygen partial pressure returns high enough, MoB phase re-condenses again leaving a more viscous B-depleted silica glass on the top. Little amount of Mo-based phases managed to stream to the surface and few MoO₃ crystals were found, Fig. 6g.

5. Conclusions

ZrB₂ ceramics sintered with 15 vol% of various transition metal disilicides, such as Zr, Mo, Ta and W, were oxidized in a bottom-up loading furnace in the temperature range 1200-1800°C for 15 minutes in order to define which additive is better in each temperature regime. The measure of the thickness of the oxidized cross section and the specific weight gain gave compatible results and the following conclusions were pointed out:

1. Zr, Mo, Ta and W do not clearly modify the outermost glass features, as found by other authors in the case of Ta.
2. WSi₂ and ZrSi₂ have similar influence on the oxidation behavior of ZrB₂, at least up to 1650°C. The expected superior oxidation resistance in case of WSi₂ addition due to ZrO₂ scale sintering was not observed **even at 1800°C**.
3. TaSi₂ could be adequately used up to 1500°C, but above the abrupt gas evolution and the remarked volume expansion of the mixed oxide render this additive not suitable for ZrB₂.
4. MoSi₂ was by far the best additive to improve the oxidation resistance of ZrB₂, due its superior stability during the sintering stage and high temperature exposition in air and due to its ability to form stable solid compounds, like MoB, in the subsurface layer. Limited gaseous species developed and, as a consequence, no formation of columnar ZrO₂ was observed **up to 1650°C. The total oxidized scale at 1800°C was thinner than in the other composites at 1650°C.**

Acknowledgements

D. Dalle Fabbriche (CNR-ISTEC, Faenza), J. Watts and E. Newman (MS&T, Rolla) are greatly acknowledged for oxidation tests. Experiments at 1800°C have been carried out through the NSF grant “Materials World Network Program, Cooperative activity in materials research between USA and Italy: Dual composite ceramics for improved properties”.

References

1. R.A. Cutler, Engineering properties of borides, in: S.J. Schneider (Ed.), *Ceramics and Glasses: Engineered Materials Handbook*, Vol. 4., ASM International, Materials Park, 1991, pp. 787-803.
2. W.G. Fahrenholtz, G.E. Hilmas, I.G. Talmy and J.A. Zaykoski, Refractory diborides of zirconium and hafnium, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 90 (2007) 1347-1364.
3. A.L. Chamberlain, W.G. Fahrenholtz, G.E. Hilmas, D.T. Ellerby, High Strength ZrB₂-Based Ceramics, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 87 (2004) 1170-1172.
4. William G. Fahrenholtz, Eric W. Neuman, Harlan J. Brown-Shaklee, and Gregory E. Hilmas, Superhard Boride–Carbide Particulate Composites, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 93 (2010) 3580–3583.
5. D. Sciti, L. Silvestroni, C. Melandri, G. Celotti, S. Guicciardi, Sintering and mechanical properties of ZrB₂-TaSi₂ and HfB₂-TaSi₂ ceramic composites, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 91 (2008) 3285–3291.
6. J. Zou, G.J. Zhang, C.F. Hu, T. Nishimura, Y. Sakka, J. Vleugels, O. Van der Biest, Strong ZrB₂-SiC-WC Ceramics at 1600°C, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 95 (2012) 874–878.
7. Eric W. Neuman, Gregory E. Hilmas, William G. Fahrenholtz, Strength of Zirconium Diboride to 2300°C, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 96 (2013) 47–50.
8. T.A. Parthasarathy, R.A. Rapp, M. Opeka, R.J. Kerans, A Model for the Oxidation of ZrB₂, HfB₂ and TiB₂. *Acta Mater.* 55 (2007) 5999–6010.
9. H. Okamoto, O-Zr (Oxygen-Zirconium), *J. Phase Equil. Diff.* 28 (2007) 498.
10. A. Rezaie, W.G. Fahrenholtz, G.E. Hilmas, Evolution of Structure During the Oxidation of Zirconium Diboride – Silicon Carbide in Air up to 1500°C, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 27(2007) 2495-2501.
11. X.H. Zhang, P. Hu, J.C. Han, Structure evolution of ZrB₂-SiC during the oxidation in air. *J. Mater. Res.* 23 (2008) 1961-1972.
12. P. Hu, W. Guolin, Z. Wang, Oxidation mechanism and resistance of ZrB₂-SiC composites. *Corros. Sci.* 51 (2009) 2724-2732.
13. S.N. Karlsdottir, J.W. Halloran, Oxidation of ZrB₂-SiC: influence of SiC content on solid and liquid oxide phase formation, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 92 (2009) 481–486.
14. S.R. Levine, E.J. Opila, M.C. Halbig, J.D. Kiser, M. Singh, J.A. Salem, Evaluation of Ultra-High Temperature Ceramics for Aero propulsion Use, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 22 (2002) 2757-2767.
15. I.G. Talmy, J.A. Zaykoski, M.M. Opeka, High Temperature Chemistry and Oxidation of ZrB₂ Ceramics Containing SiC, Si₃N₄, Ta₅Si₃ and TaSi₂, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 91 (2008) 2250-2257.
16. P. Hu, X.H. Zhang, J.C. Han, X.G. Luo, S.Y. Du, Effect of Various Additives on the Oxidation Behavior of ZrB₂-Based Ultra-High-Temperature Ceramics at 1800°C. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 93 (2010) 345-349.
17. S.C. Zhang, G.E. Hilmas, W.G. Fahrenholtz, Improved oxidation resistance of zirconium diboride by tungsten carbide additions, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 91 (2008) 3530-3535.

18. V.A. Lavrenko, A.D. Panasyuk, T.C. Protsenko, V.P. Dyatel, E.S. Lugovskaya, E.I. Egorova, High temperature reactions of materials of the ZrB_2 - $ZrSi_2$ system with oxygen, *Porosh. Metall.* 6 (1982) 56-58.
19. D.Sciti, M. Brach, A. Bellosi, Oxidation behavior of a pressureless sintered ZrB_2 - $MoSi_2$ ceramic composite, *J. Mater. Res.* 20 (2005) 922-930.
20. D. Sciti, M. Brach, A. Bellosi, Long term Oxidation behaviour and mechanical strength degradation of a pressureless sintered ZrB_2 - $MoSi_2$ ceramic, *Scripta Mater.* 53 (2005) 1297-1302.
21. D. Sciti, V. Medri, L. Silvestroni, Oxidation behaviour of HfB_2 -15 vol.% $TaSi_2$ at low, intermediate and high temperatures, *Scripta Mater.* 63 (2010) 601-604.
22. M. Kazemzadeh Dehdashti, W.G. Fahrenholtz, G.E. Hilmas, Effects of temperature and the incorporation of W on the oxidation of ZrB_2 ceramics, *Corros. Sci.* 80 (2014) 221-228.
23. V.O. Lavrenko, A.D. Panasyuk, O.M. Grigorev, O.V. Koroteev, V.A. Kotenko, High-Temperature oxidation of ZrB_2 - SiC and ZrB_2 - SiC - $ZrSi_2$ ceramics 1700°C in air, *Powder Metallurgy and Metal Ceram.* 51 (2012) 217-221.
24. O.N. Grigoriev, B.A. Galanov, V.A. Lavrenko, A.D. Panasyuk, S.M. Ivanov, A.V. Koroteev, K.G. Nickel, Oxidation of ZrB_2 - SiC - $ZrSi_2$ ceramics in oxygen, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 30 (2010) 2397-2405.
25. S. Guo, T. Mizuguchi, M. Ikegami, Y. Kagawa, Oxidation behavior of ZrB_2 - $MoSi_2$ - SiC composites in air at 1500 C, *Ceram. Intern.* 37 (2011) 585-591.
26. H. Pastor, R. Meyer, An Investigation of the Effect of Additions of Metal Silicides on Titanium and Zirconium Borides from the Point of View of their Sintering Behavior and their Resistance to Oxidation at High Temperature, *Rev. Int. Htes Temp. Refract.* 2 (1974) 41-54.
27. F. Peng, R. F. Speyer, Oxidation Resistance of Fully Dense ZrB_2 with SiC , TaB_2 , and $TaSi_2$ Additives, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 91 (2008) 1489-1494.
28. E. Opila, S. Levine, J. Lorincz, Oxidation of ZrB_2 and HfB_2 -Based Ultra-High Temperature Ceramics: Effect of Ta Additions, *J. Mat. Sci.*, 39 (2004) 5969-5977.
29. I.G. Talmy, J.A. Zaykoski, M.M. Opeka, A.H. Smith, Properties of Ceramics in the System ZrB_2 - Ta_5Si_3 , *J. Mat. Res.* 21 (2006) 2593-2599.
30. S.C. Zhang, W.G. Fahrenholtz, G.E. Hilmas, Oxidation of ZrB_2 and ZrB_2 - SiC ceramic with Tungsten additions", *Electrochem. Soc. Transac.* 16 (2009) 137-145.
31. D.G. Barton, S.L. Soled, G.D. Meitzner, G.A. Fuentes, E. Iglesia, Structural and Catalytic Characterization of Solid Acids Based on Zirconia Modified by Tungsten Oxide, *J. Catalysis* 181 (1999) 57-72.
32. L. Silvestroni, H.J. Kleebe, S. Lauterbach, M. Müller, D. Sciti, Transmission Electron Microscopy on Zr- and Hf-borides with $MoSi_2$ addition: Densification Mechanisms, *J. Mat. Res.* 25 (2010) 828-834.
33. H. Okamoto, The Zr-Si System, *Bull. Alloy Phase diagrams*, 11 (1990) 513-519.

34. L.Y. Chang, M.G. Scroger, B. Phillips, Condensed Phase Relations in the Systems ZrO_2 - WO_2 - WO_3 and HfO_2 - WO_2 - WO_3 , *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 50 (1967) 211–215.
35. H.A. Wriedt, The O-W (oxygen-tungsten) system, *Bull. Alloy Phase Diagr.* 10 (1989) 368-384.
36. A.B. Gokhale, G.J. Abbaschian, The Mo-Si System, *J. Phase Equilib.* 12 (1991) 493-498.
37. L. Silvestroni, C. Melandri, S. Guicciardi, D. Sciti, TaB₂-based ceramics: microstructure, mechanical properties and oxidation resistance, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 32 (2012) 97–105.
38. C.M. Carney, T.A. Parthasarathy, M.K. Cinibulk, Oxidation Resistance of Hafnium Diboride Ceramics with Additions of Silicon Carbide and Tungsten Boride or Tungsten Carbide, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 94 (2011) 2600–2607.
39. D. Caurant, O. Majérus, E. Fadel, M. Lenoir, C. Gervais, O. Pinet, Effect of Molybdenum on the Structure and on the Crystallization of SiO_2 – Na_2O – CaO – B_2O_3 Glasses, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 90 (2007) 774–783.

Tables

Table I: Composition, sintering conditions and main microstructural features of the as sintered ZrB_2 - $MeSi_2$ composites. **m.g.s.:** mean grain size.

Label	MSi_2 15 vol%	Sintering °C, MPa, min	Rel. density %	ZrB_2 m.g.s. μm	Secondary phases vol%
ZBZ	$ZrSi_2$	1600,30,10	96.5	2.5	3.2 ZrO_2 , 3 Zr_xSi_y , 1.5 SiO_2 , 1.3 SiC
ZBM	$MoSi_2$	1750,30,20	99.0	2.4	$(Zr,Mo)B_2$, 14.2 $MoSi_2$, 4.0 SiO_2 , 1.5 SiC, 1.0 ZrO_2
ZBT	$TaSi_2$	1850,30,10	99.0	2.0	$(Zr,Ta)B_2$, 5.0 Ta_xSi_y , 2.0 SiO_2 , 1.6 ZrO_2 , 1.5 SiC
ZBW	WSi_2	1930,30,25	95.5	3.5	$(Zr,W)B_2$, 3.5 [WC, $(Zr,W)B$, $(W,Zr)_xSi_y$], 2.4 SiO_2 , 0.5 ZrO_2

Table II: Main crystalline phases detected by XRD on the oxidized specimens. Compounds are listed in decreasing amount.

Sample	1200°C	1350°C	1500°C	1650°C	1800°C
ZBZ	m- ZrO_2 , ZrB_2 , t- ZrO_2	m- ZrO_2 , t- ZrO_2 , ZrB_2	m- ZrO_2 , t- ZrO_2	m- ZrO_2 , t- ZrO_2	-
ZBM	m- ZrO_2 , ZrB_2 , MoB, $MoSi_2$	m- ZrO_2 , ZrB_2 , MoB, t- ZrO_2	m- ZrO_2 , ZrB_2 , MoB, t- ZrO_2	m- ZrO_2 , MoB, t- ZrO_2 , ZrB_2	m- ZrO_2 , t- ZrO_2 , MoO ₃
ZBT	m- ZrO_2 , ZrB_2 , o- $Zr_{2.75}TaO_8$, TaB_2	m- ZrO_2 , TaB_2 , o- $Zr_{2.75}TaO_8$, ZrB_2	o- $Zr_{2.75}TaO_8$ [200], m- ZrO_2 , TaB_2	o- $Zr_{2.75}TaO_8$ [020], o- Ta_2O_5 , m- ZrO_2	-
ZBW	m- ZrO_2 , ZrB_2 , t- ZrO_2	m- ZrO_2 , t- ZrO_2 , ZrB_2	m- ZrO_2 , t- ZrO_2	m- ZrO_2 , t- ZrO_2	m- ZrO_2 , t- ZrO_2

*traces

Figures' captions

Fig.1: Microstructure of the as sintered composites. a) ZBZ, b) ZBM, c) ZBT, d) ZBW.

Fig.2: From left to right appearance of the oxidized samples at 1200, 1350, 1500 and 1650°C for 15 minutes. a) ZBZ, b) ZBM, c) ZBT, d) ZBW. For ZBM and ZBW also the specimens oxidized at 1800°C are reported in the bottom.

Fig.3: Weight gain per unit surface area as a function of the oxidation temperature.

Fig. 4: X-ray diffraction patterns of ZBT after oxidation at each temperature for 15 minutes.

Fig. 5: SEM images of surface (up) and cross section (bottom) of ZBZ oxidized at a) 1200, b) 1350, c) 1500, d) 1650°C with microstructural details in the insets.

Fig. 6: SEM images of surface (up) and cross section (bottom) of ZBM oxidized at a) 1200, b) 1350, c) 1500, d) 1650°C with microstructural details in the insets. e) External surface and f) cross section of ZBM oxidized at 1800°C with microstructural details as indicated.

Fig. 7: SEM images of surface (up) and cross section (bottom) of ZBT oxidized at a) 1200, b) 1350, c) 1500, d) 1650°C with microstructural details in the insets.

Fig. 8: SEM images of surface (up) and cross section (bottom) of ZBW oxidized at a) 1200, b) 1350, c) 1500, d) 1650°C with microstructural details in the insets. e) Surface and f)-g) cross section of ZBW oxidized at 1800°C with microstructural details as indicated.

Fig. 9: Plot of the modified thickness in the ZrB₂-based samples as a function of the oxidation temperature.

Fig. 10: Sketch of the oxidation phenomena occurring in the ZrB₂-based composites during oxidation in the 1200-1650°C temperature range. a) ZBZ, b) ZBM, c) ZBT, d) ZBW.

Figure 1
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 2
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 3
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 4
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 5
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 6
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 7
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 8
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 9
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 10

[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

